

OCEAN ICE News – June 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to June's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, including the webinars which are hosted by the European Polar Board, highlighting May and June's Climate Coffee and the CCAMLR Meeting at BAS. We have an upcoming Climate Coffee that you can register for in September. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in July!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Natalia Shepel

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Natalia Shepel, an Oceanographer at [National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine](#).

Read the feature on Natalia [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE Celebrating World Bicycle Day: 3 June 2025

As part of my Carbon Literacy Training last year, I developed a personal Action Plan with a pledge: to celebrate World Bicycle Day on 3rd June 2025 by encouraging as many people as possible to cycle to work - or after work - in support of sustainable travel. This initiative aimed to reduce our collective carbon footprint while promoting healthier, more active lifestyles. In the lead-up to the day, I shared the initiative within the OCEAN ICE project community to help maximise participation and visibility.

I'm thrilled to share that a number of colleagues took to their bikes and joined the ride in honour of World Bicycle Day across the UK, Germany, and Norway. One particularly inspiring participant cycled an impressive 55 km to work - proof that determination and commitment to the cause truly go a long way! I've created a collage of photos to celebrate everyone who took part - thank you all for making the effort and embracing the spirit of sustainable transport.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Webinar Series

The OCEAN ICE webinar series, hosted by the European Polar Board, is set to continue! The webinars offer insights into the OCEAN ICE project, showcasing ongoing research, key findings, and expected outcomes from various work packages.

On the 13th of May, EPB presented a webinar for WP4 on Quantification of Antarctic ice sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes, here's a summary on what the webinar covered:

This is the fourth webinar in the series introducing the OCEAN:ICE project. In this session, we explore Work Package 4 (WP4), which focuses on quantifying deep uncertainty in the Antarctic ice sheet and freshwater fluxes under climate forcing, which is one of the key focuses of the project.. This webinar features talks by:

- Jan De Rydt (Northumbria University) - Introduction to Work Package 4)
- Vio Coulon (Université Libre de Bruxelles) - Future Freshwater Fluxes from the Antarctic Ice Sheet
- Qing Qin (Northumbria University) - Calibration of Ice-Sheet Melt Parameterizations
- Frank Pattyn (Université Libre de Bruxelles) - Deep Uncertainty in Freshwater Fluxes

The webinar concludes with a public Q&A session.

Catch up on the webinar here: [OCEAN ICE WP4 Webinar - Quantification of Antarctic ice sheet deep uncertainty and freshwater fluxes under Climate forcing](#)

Don't miss out - join the conversation and stay informed about the latest developments of the project.

OCEAN:ICE **EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD**

OCEAN ICE WP4 WEBINAR

QUANTIFICATION OF ANTARCTIC ICE SHEET DEEP UNCERTAINTY AND FRESHWATER FLUXES UNDER CLIMATE FORCING

This webinar will be the fourth in a series introducing the EU-funded OCEAN ICE project.

Register here:

13 May 2025
10:30 CEST

© Dr. Renuka Bache

Funded by the European Union

UKRI UK Research and Innovation

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – May and June

Catch up on May's Climate Coffee with Inga Sauer on Extreme weather events: tipping points & societal implications [here](#).

The poverty implications of increasing frequencies of extreme weather events - identifying tipping points across households from different income groups

Abstract: The frequency of extreme weather events is projected to increase in many world regions under climate change. However, the societal implications of these higher event frequencies are far less understood, as the short- and long-term impacts of extreme events such as floods and tropical cyclones are commonly studied for individual extremes. It is generally assumed that the impacts of extreme events with overlapping socio-economic repercussions are likely to differ from the cumulative impacts of independent events. Yet, a comprehensive quantitative understanding of the potential non-linear impacts of increased event frequencies remains widely absent. Critical thresholds that, when surpassed, cause non-linear transitions in social systems to a qualitatively different state are often referred to as social tipping points. Here, we assess whether increasing frequencies of weather extremes can trigger the social tipping of households, defined as a transition from a non-poor state that allows for self-reliant recovery to a poverty trap that hinders further independent recovery. To this end, we employ an agent-based model accounting for the recovery dynamics of households affected by consecutive extreme events. We assess the effect of incomplete recoveries in between recurrent extremes in terms of consumption and well-being losses as well as critical event frequencies inducing tipping across households from different income groups. We find that middle-income households are most sensitive to being trapped in poverty due to increased event frequencies and associated incomplete recovery. High-income households can mostly afford a self-reliant recovery even under high event frequencies, while poor households are often trapped in poverty by individual events. Finally, we explore the implications of these household tipping dynamics for societal inequality.

22 May 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online
Inga Sauer (PIK)

Extreme weather events: tipping points and societal implications

The poverty implications of increasing frequencies of extreme weather events -
identifying tipping points across households from different income groups

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Catch up on June's Climate Coffee with Pietro Viglino: Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, Drawing on OCEAN ICE experience [here](#).

What this webinar is about: The Horizon Europe-funded project OCEAN ICE adheres to open science practices and supports the publication of complementary materials that facilitate the reuse of the project's data. One key tool is the OCEAN ICE literacy portal, which provides instructions and examples about creating new research products using Jupyter Notebooks, which are openly available for testing and further use. In this talk, after a short introduction about how to interact with OCEAN ICE's data service (ERDDAP) using Python, the participants will be guided through the exploration of these data and their visualization in a Jupyter environment. In this way, the participants will obtain the tools to play with code using the same data typology that is used in the Notebooks available in open access for the OCEAN ICE project.

Climate Coffee

12 June 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST

Online

Pietro Viglino (ETT)

**Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement
them, drawing on the experience in the
OCEAN ICE project**

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

OCEAN ICE presented at CCAMLR

On the 31st of March this year, the Commission for the Conservation of Marine Living Organisms (CCAMLR) held a scientific priorities workshop at the British Antarctic Survey in Cambridge, UK. CCAMLR is an international body that sets catch quotas, manages marine protected areas and assesses the sustainability of fishing and other commercial activities south of 60S in Antarctic waters. It is very much evidence based and operates on the precautionary principle, so the CCAMLR science advisory group is a valuable part of the process.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE - Water isotope coordination in OCEAN ICE and beyond Cross-Cutting Theme Meeting

Xabier Davila has used the TMI inverse model and historical interior observations of temperature, salinity and d18O to reconstruct past surface distributions and trends of these three tracers. The reconstruction goes back several centuries in some regions, although focus is placed on the multi-decadal timescale. Promising agreement with independent products, where available.

Isotopic tracing of East Antarctic Ice Sheet-Southern Ocean dynamics over the Common Era (ISO-TRACE) is a three-year project submitted a few weeks ago to the French ANR and German DFG agencies. It is a collaboration between LOCEAN, LSCE, AWI and Kiel University. The project aims to produce the first continuous records of sea surface water isotopes, temperature and salinity over the last 500 to 2000 years in the vicinity of the Antarctic continent. These records will be used to ground-truth model simulations and reconstruct the history of East Antarctic Ice Sheet melting. A first task will analyze instrumental data in the Indian sector of the Southern Ocean. A second task will analyze sediment cores retrieved at multiple sites in the same sector from the open ocean to the coast. A third task will carry model simulations with isotope-enabled ocean (NEMO) and atmosphere (LMDZ) models.

Sessions devoted to water and carbon isotope observations will take place at the next Ocean Sciences Meeting in Glasgow (February 2026). Kathryn Gunn mentions that some new samples for water isotope data were collected on the Ross Sea shelf in January 2025. They have not been analyzed yet due to lab delays but should be processed in the coming few months. Cross-calibration with LOCEAN is planned. The samples were collected as part of the FRESH initiative. The overall aim is to diagnose the sources of freshwater in the region. Contact Kathryn Gunn for more info about the data

OCEAN ICE Publication: Antarctic Ice Sheet tipping in the last 800,000 years warns of future ice loss

A recent OCEAN ICE publication has been published in Nature examines how the Antarctic Ice Sheet has responded to past climate changes and what that means for future sea-level rise. The study suggests that the Antarctic Ice Sheet may already be in a vulnerable state, close to or beyond the tipping point, even without significant additional warming.

This article features David M. Chandler, Petra M. Langebroek, Torsten Albrecht from OCEAN ICE.

Read the article [here](#).

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in September, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Audrey Minière on Estimating ocean warming: Challenges & recommendations for robust assessment

25 September 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

25 September 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Audrey Minière (ENS)

Estimating ocean warming: challenges
and recommendations for robust
assessment

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 2-13 June 2025, [United Nations Ocean Conference \(UNOC3\)](#), Nice
- 20-25 July 2025, [Busan IAMAS-IACS-IAPSO Joint Assembly 2025 \(JMCP20\)](#), the Republic of Korea
- 16-18 June 2025, [FRISP](#), in Rovaniemi, Finland

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452.